

On Brousseau summation of Narayana numbers

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Abstract

In this paper, we find both recursion and closed form formulas for the convolution $\sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_{n-i}$ for all integers $m \geq 0$, where G_n are the generalized Narayana numbers defined by the third order linear recurrence $G_n = G_{n-1} + G_{n-3}$ for $n \geq 3$ with arbitrary integer initial terms $G_0 = a$, $G_1 = b$, and $G_2 = c$. Using this, we find closed-form formulas for the Brousseau sums $\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i$ and the shifted Brousseau sums $\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i}$ for all integers $m, r \geq 0$.

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1 Introduction

Narayana's cows sequence $(N_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is defined by the third-order linear recurrence

$$N_n = N_{n-1} + N_{n-3},$$

for $n \geq 3$ with initial terms $N_0 = 0$ and $N_1 = N_2 = 1$. This sequence is A000930 in [12]. We consider a generalized form of the Narayana sequence $(G_n)_{n \geq 0}$ defined by

$$G_n = G_{n-1} + G_{n-3}, \tag{1}$$

for $n \geq 3$ with initial terms $G_0 = a$, $G_1 = b$, and $G_2 = c$. Here a, b , and c are arbitrary integers with $(a, b, c) \neq (0, 0, 0)$. The generalized Narayana numbers can be extended to negative indices by

$$G_n = G_{n+3} - G_{n+2},$$

for $n < 0$. Narayana-Lucas sequence (A001609 in [12]) and Narayana-Perrin sequence are defined by the same recurrence with $(a, b, c) = (3, 1, 1)$ and $(a, b, c) = (3, 0, 2)$, respectively. See Soykan [11] for further information on the generalized Narayana sequence.

In this paper, we are interested in finding closed-form expressions for the weighted sums

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{i+r},$$

where m and r are non-negative integers. Similar types of sums involving the classical Fibonacci numbers F_i (A000045 in [12]) were first studied by Brousseau [3, 4]. Many authors have attempted to find an exact formula for the sum,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i^m F_i,$$

using various techniques. These methods include linear recurrence relations, the finite difference approach, linear operators, and matrix methods (see [6], [8], [13]). Recently, Ollerton and Shannon [9], Shannon and Ollerton [10], Dresden [5], and Adegoke [1] derived expressions for such sums. Dresden [5] used a novel approach involving only binomial coefficients to compute the sum $\sum_{i=0}^n i^m F_i$. We use a similar technique as that of Dresden [5] to find the Brousseau sums of generalized Narayana numbers.

Throughout this paper, we assume that $\binom{0}{0} = 1$ and $0^0 = 1$.

2 Narayana numbers and Powers

We begin with the following set of identities:

$$\begin{aligned} N_n - N_{n-1} &= n^1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^1 - 3 \cdot \binom{1}{1} \cdot i^0 \right) N_{n-i} \\ N_n + N_{n-1} &= n^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^2 - 3 \cdot \binom{2}{1} \cdot i^1 + 3 \cdot \binom{2}{2} \cdot i^0 \right) N_{n-i} \\ N_n - N_{n-1} &= n^3 + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^3 - 3 \cdot \binom{3}{1} \cdot i^2 + 3 \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot i^1 - 9 \cdot \binom{3}{3} \cdot i^0 \right) N_{n-i} \\ N_n + N_{n-1} &= n^4 + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^4 - 3 \cdot \binom{4}{1} \cdot i^3 + 3 \cdot \binom{4}{2} \cdot i^2 - 9 \cdot \binom{4}{3} \cdot i^1 + 15 \cdot \binom{4}{4} \cdot i^0 \right) N_{n-i} \end{aligned}$$

The generalization of these identities is our first theorem.

Theorem 2.1. *For all integers $n \geq 1$ and $n \geq 1$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} G_n &= a(n+1)^m + (b-a)n^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i}. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Proof. We proceed by induction on n . When $n = 1$, the left-hand side of (2) is

$$G_1 = b,$$

and the right-hand side is

$$\begin{aligned} a \cdot 2^m + (b-a) - (-1)^m G_0 + \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \right) G_0 \\ = a \cdot 2^m + (b-a) - a(-1)^m + a(1 - 2^m + (-1)^m) \\ = b. \end{aligned}$$

When $n = 2$, the left-hand side of (2) is

$$G_2 = c,$$

and the right-hand side is

$$\begin{aligned} a \cdot 3^m + (b-a)2^m + (c-b) - (-1)^m G_1 + \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \right) G_1 \\ + \left(2^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) 2^{m-j} \binom{m}{j} \right) G_0 \\ = a \cdot 3^m + (b-a)2^m + (c-b) - b(-1)^m + b(1 - 2^m + (-1)^m) + a(2^m - 3^m) \\ = c. \end{aligned}$$

When $n = 3$, the left- hand side of (2) is

$$G_3 = a + c,$$

and the right-hand side is

$$\begin{aligned} & a \cdot 4^m + (b - a)3^m + (c - b)2^m - (-1)^m G_2 + \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j}\right) G_2 \\ & + \left(2^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) 2^{m-j} \binom{m}{j}\right) G_1 + \left(3^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) 3^{m-j} \binom{m}{j}\right) G_0 \\ & = a \cdot 4^m + (b - a)3^m + (c - b)2^m - c(-1)^m + c(1 - 2^m + (-1)^m) + b(2^m - 3^m) \\ & + a(3^m - 4^m + 1) \\ & = a + c. \end{aligned}$$

Now, set $n \geq 4$. Assume that (2) holds for all non-negative integers less than n . Then

$$\begin{aligned} G_{n-1} &= a n^m + (b - a)(n - 1)^m + (c - b)(n - 2)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-2} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} G_{n-3} &= a(n - 2)^m + (b - a)(n - 3)^m + (c - b)(n - 4)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-4} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n-3} \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i-3}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Since $G_{-1} = c - b$ and $G_{-2} = b - a$, we can rewrite (4) as

$$\begin{aligned} G_{n-3} &= a(n - 2)^m + (b - a)(n - 3)^m + (c - b)(n - 4)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-4} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i-3} \\ &- (c - b)((n - 2)^m - (n - 1)^m + (n - 4)^m) \\ &- (b - a)((n - 1)^m - n^m + (n - 3)^m). \end{aligned}$$

This simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} G_{n-3} &= (b - a)n^m + (a - 2b + c)(n - 1)^m + (a - c + b)(n - 2)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-4} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i-3}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Adding (3) and (5), and using the Narayana recursion, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} G_n &= b n^m + (c - b)(n - 1)^m + a(n - 2)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Since $G_0 = a$, we can rewrite (6) as

$$\begin{aligned} G_n &= b n^m + (c - b)(n - 1)^m + a(n - 2)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i} - a(n^m - (n + 1)^m + (n - 2)^m) \\ &= a(n + 1)^m + (b - a)n^m + (c - b)(n - 1)^m + b n^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^n \left(i^m - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} \right) G_{n-i}, \end{aligned}$$

as desired. This completes the induction step. $\square$

3 Recursion

Using Theorem 2.1, we can derive a recursion formula for finding the convolution $\sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_{n-i}$ of the Narayana numbers and powers.

Definition 3.1. For all integers $n \geq 1$, we define

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=0}^n G_{n-i}, & \text{if } m = 0 ; \\ \sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_{n-i}, & \text{if } m \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3.2. For all integers $m \geq 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} = & (-2)^m G_n + (-1)^m G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^m - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \mathcal{T}_n^{(m-j)}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)}$ is as defined in Definition 3.1.

Proof. Rewriting (2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} G_n = & a(n+1)^m + (b-a)n^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{n-i} - \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} G_{n-i}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Set $m \geq 1$. Since $0^m G_n = 0$ we may begin the summand $\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{n-i}$ at $i = 0$ instead of at $i = 1$. Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} G_n = & a(n+1)^m + (b-a)n^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_{n-i} - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \sum_{i=1}^n i^{m-j} G_{n-i}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Now, using the fact

$$\sum_{i=0}^m i^{m-j} G_{n-i} = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m i^{m-j} G_{n-i}, & \text{if } j \neq m ; \\ G_n + \sum_{i=1}^m i^{m-j} G_{n-i}, & \text{if } j = m, \end{cases}$$

we can rewrite (9) as

$$\begin{aligned} G_n = & a(n+1)^m + (b-a)n^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m - (-1)^m G_{n-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_{n-i} - \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \sum_{i=0}^n i^{m-j} G_{n-i} + (1 - (-2)^m) G_n. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_{n-i} = & (-2)^m G_n + (-1)^m G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^m - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \sum_{i=0}^n i^{m-j} G_{n-i}, \end{aligned}$$

as desired. This completes the proof. $\square$

4 Convolution

It follows from [11, Proposition 6.1] that

$$\sum_{i=0}^n G_i = G_{n+3} - c.$$

We can rewrite this as

$$\sum_{i=0}^n G_i = G_{n+1} + G_n + G_{n-1} - c. \quad (10)$$

Therefore,

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(0)} = \sum_{i=0}^n G_{n-i} = 1 \cdot G_{n+1} + 1 \cdot G_n + 1 \cdot G_{n-1} - c. \quad (11)$$

Now, using Theorem 3.2 and (11), we can find the expressions for the convolutions $\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)}$ recursively for $m = 1, 2, \dots$. For example, setting $m = 1$ in (7) yields

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(1)} = -2 \cdot G_n - G_{n-1} - a(n+1) - (b-a)n - (c-b)(n-1) + 3 \cdot \mathcal{T}_n^{(0)}.$$

Now, using (11), this becomes

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(1)} = 3 \cdot G_{n+1} + 1 \cdot G_n + 2 \cdot G_{n-1} - (cn + a + b + 2c). \quad (12)$$

Setting $m = 2$ in (7), we get

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(2)} = 4 \cdot G_n + G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^2 - (b-a)n^2 - (c-b)(n-1)^2 + 6 \cdot \mathcal{T}_n^{(1)} - 3 \cdot \mathcal{T}_n^{(0)}.$$

Substituting (11) and (12), this becomes

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(2)} = 15 \cdot G_{n+1} + 7 \cdot G_n + 10 \cdot G_{n-1} - (cn^2 + 2(a+b+2c)n + 7a + 5b + 10c). \quad (13)$$

If we take N_n as a representative, we obtain the following convolution identities:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^n N_{n-i} &= 1 \cdot N_{n+1} + 1 \cdot N_n + 1 \cdot N_{n-1} - 1 \\ \sum_{i=0}^n i N_{n-i} &= 3 \cdot N_{n+1} + 1 \cdot N_n + 2 \cdot N_{n-1} - (n+3) \\ \sum_{i=0}^n i^2 N_{n-i} &= 15 \cdot N_{n+1} + 7 \cdot N_n + 10 \cdot N_{n-1} - (n^2 + 6n + 15) \\ \sum_{i=0}^n i^3 N_{n-i} &= 117 \cdot N_{n+1} + 55 \cdot N_n + 80 \cdot N_{n-1} - (n^3 + 9n^2 + 45n + 117) \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} n+3 &= 1 \cdot \binom{1}{0} \cdot n^1 + 3 \cdot \binom{1}{1} \cdot n^0 \\ n^2 + 6n + 15 &= 1 \cdot \binom{2}{0} \cdot n^2 + 3 \cdot \binom{2}{1} \cdot n + 15 \cdot \binom{2}{2} \cdot n^0 \\ n^3 + 9n^2 + 45n + 117 &= 1 \cdot \binom{3}{0} \cdot n^3 + 3 \cdot \binom{3}{1} \cdot n^2 + 15 \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot n + 117 \cdot \binom{3}{3} \cdot n^0 \end{aligned}$$

To understand the pattern in the above identities about the convolutions, we must define the following three sequences of numbers:

Definition 4.1. We define the integer sequences $(A^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$, $(B^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$, and $(C^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$ as follows:

$$A^{(m)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } m = 0 ; \\ \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} A^{(m-j)}, & \text{if } m \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

$$B^{(m)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } m = 0 ; \\ (-2)^m + \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} B^{(m-j)}, & \text{if } m \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

$$C^{(m)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } m = 0 ; \\ (-1)^m + \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} C^{(m-j)}, & \text{if } m \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

The first seven terms of these sequences are given in Table 1.

m	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
$A^{(m)}$	1	3	15	117	1227	16053	251955
$B^{(m)}$	1	1	7	55	571	7471	117307
$C^{(m)}$	1	2	10	80	838	10952	171910

Table 1: Terms of $A^{(m)}$, $B^{(m)}$, and $C^{(m)}$

Theorem 4.2. For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} = A^{(m)}G_{n+1} + B^{(m)}G_n + C^{(m)}G_{n-1} + an^m - \sum_{j=0}^m (bA^{(j)} + aB^{(j)} + (c-b)C^{(j)}) \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}. \quad (14)$$

Proof. We proceed by induction on m . The case where $m = 0$ follows from identity (10). Now, set $m \geq 1$. Assume that (14) holds for all non-negative integers less than m . Using Theorem 3.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} = & (-2)^m G_n + (-1)^m G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^m - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} \mathcal{T}_n^{(m-j)}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Now, by induction hypothesis, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_n^{(m-j)} = & A^{(m-j)}G_{n+1} + B^{(m-j)}G_n + C^{(m-j)}G_{n-1} + an^{m-j} \\ & - \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m-j}{r} n^{m-j-r}, \end{aligned}$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Substituting this in (15) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} &= (-2)^m G_n + (-1)^m G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^m - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} (A^{(m-j)} G_{n+1} + B^{(m-j)} G_n + C^{(m-j)} G_{n-1} + an^{m-j}) \\
&- \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m-j}{r} n^{m-j-r} \\
&= (-2)^m G_n + (-1)^m G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^m - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} A^{(m-j)} G_{n+1} + \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} B^{(m-j)} G_n \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} C^{(m-j)} G_{n-1} + a \cdot \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j} \\
&- \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m-j}{r} n^{m-j-r}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, using Definition 4.1 and the identity

$$\sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j} = (n+1)^m - (n-2)^m,$$

this becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} &= (-2)^m G_n + (-1)^m G_{n-1} - a(n+1)^m - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m + A^{(m)} G_{n+1} \\
&+ B^{(m)} G_n - (-2)^m G_n + C^{(m)} G_{n-1} - (-1)^m G_{n-1} + a((n+1)^m - (n-2)^m) \\
&- \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (1 - (-2)^j) (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r} n^{m-j-r} \\
&= A^{(m)} G_{n+1} + B^{(m)} G_n + C^{(m)} G_{n-1} - (b-a)n^m - (c-b)(n-1)^m - a(n-2)^m \\
&- \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (1 - (-2)^j) (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r} n^{m-j-r}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(m)} = A^{(m)} G_{n+1} + B^{(m)} G_n + C^{(m)} G_{n-1} + an^m - \psi^{(m)}(n),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi^{(m)}(n) &= bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m + a(n-2)^m \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (1 - (-2)^j) (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r} n^{m-j-r} \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

We can complete the induction step by showing that

$$\psi^{(m)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^m (bA^{(j)} + aB^{(j)} + (c-b)C^{(j)}) \binom{m}{j} n^{(m-j)}.$$

If we execute the change of variable $r' = r + j$ in (16), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi^{(m)}(n) &= bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m + a(n-2)^m \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r'=j}^m (1 - (-2)^j) (bA^{(r'-j)} + aB^{(r'-j)} + (c-b)C^{(r'-j)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r'-j} n^{m-r'}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, using the binomial identity (see [2, Identity 134])

$$\binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r'-j} = \binom{m}{r'} \binom{r'}{j},$$

and switching the order of summation, this becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{(m)}(n) &= bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m + a(n-2)^m \\ &+ \sum_{r'=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^{r'} (1 - (-2)^j) (bA^{(r'-j)} + aB^{(r'-j)} + (c-b)C^{(r'-j)}) \binom{m}{r'} \binom{r'}{j} n^{m-r'} \\ &= bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m + a(n-2)^m \\ &+ \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} \sum_{j=1}^{r'} (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{r'}{j} (bA^{(r'-j)} + aB^{(r'-j)} + (c-b)C^{(r'-j)}). \end{aligned}$$

Using the Definition 4.1, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{(m)}(n) &= bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m + a(n-2)^m \\ &+ \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} \left(bA^{(r')} + a(B^{(r')} - (-2)^{r'}) + (c-b)(C^{(r')} - (-1)^{r'}) \right) \\ &= bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m + a(n-2)^m \\ &+ \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} \left(bA^{(r')} + aB^{(r')} + (c-b)C^{(r')} \right) \\ &- a \cdot \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} (-2)^{r'} - (c-b) \cdot \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} (-1)^{r'} \\ &= \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} (bA^{(r')} + aB^{(r')} + (c-b)C^{(r')}) + bn^m + (c-b)(n-1)^m \\ &+ a(n-2)^m - a((n-2)^m - n^m) - (c-b)((n-1)^m - n^m) \\ &= \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'} (bA^{(r')} + aB^{(r')} + (c-b)C^{(r')}) + (b+a+(c-b))n^m \\ &= \sum_{r'=0}^m (bA^{(r')} + aB^{(r')} + (c-b)C^{(r')}) \binom{m}{r'} n^{m-r'}, \end{aligned}$$

as desired. This completes the induction step. □

Corollary 4.3. *For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\sum_{i=0}^n i^m N_{n-i} = A^{(m)} N_{n+1} + B^{(m)} N_n + C^{(m)} N_{n-1} - \sum_{j=0}^m A^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}.$$

Proof. It follows from Theorem 4.2 by setting $G_n \equiv N_n$ and $(a, b, c) = (0, 1, 1)$. □

5 Brousseau sums

Using Theorem 4.2, we can find the Brousseau sums, $\sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_i$, of the Narayana numbers. For example,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=0}^n i^2 G_i &= \sum_{i=0}^n (n-i)^2 G_{n-i} \\
&= n^2 \sum_{i=0}^n G_{n-i} - 2n \sum_{i=0}^n i G_{n-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n i^2 G_{n-i} \\
&= n^2 (G_{n+1} + G_n + G_{n-1} - c) - 2n (3G_{n+1} + G_n + 2G_{n-1} - (cn + a + b + 2c)) \\
&\quad + 15G_{n+1} + 7G_n + 10G_{n-1} - (cn^2 + 2(a+b+2c)n + 7a + 5b + 10c) \\
&= (n^2 - 6n + 15)G_{n+1} + (n^2 - 2n + 7)G_n + (n^2 - 4n + 10)G_{n-1} - (7a + 5b + 10c).
\end{aligned}$$

If we take N_n as a representative, we obtain the following set of identities:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=0}^n N_i &= 1 \cdot N_{n+1} + 1 \cdot N_n + 1 \cdot N_{n-1} - 1 \\
\sum_{i=0}^n i N_i &= (n-3) \cdot N_{n+1} + (n-1) \cdot N_n + (n-2) \cdot N_{n-1} + 3 \\
\sum_{i=0}^n i^2 N_i &= (n^2 - 6n + 15) \cdot N_{n+1} + (n^2 - 2n + 7) \cdot N_n + (n^2 - 4n + 10) \cdot N_{n-1} - 15 \\
\sum_{i=0}^n i^3 N_i &= (n^3 - 9n^2 + 45n - 117) \cdot N_{n+1} + (n^3 - 3n^2 + 21n - 55) \cdot N_n \\
&\quad + (n^3 - 6n^2 + 30n - 80) \cdot N_{n-1} + 117
\end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned}
n-3 &= 1 \cdot \binom{1}{0} \cdot n^1 - 3 \cdot \binom{1}{1} \cdot n^0 \\
n^2 - 6n + 15 &= 1 \cdot \binom{2}{0} \cdot n^2 - 13 \cdot \binom{2}{1} \cdot n^1 + 15 \cdot \binom{2}{2} \cdot n^0 \\
n^3 - 9n^2 + 45n - 117 &= 1 \cdot \binom{3}{0} \cdot n^3 + 3 \cdot \binom{3}{1} \cdot n^2 + 15 \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot n^1 + 117 \cdot \binom{3}{3} \cdot n^0 \\
n-1 &= 1 \cdot \binom{1}{0} \cdot n^1 - 1 \cdot \binom{1}{1} \cdot n^0 \\
n^2 - 2n + 7 &= 1 \cdot \binom{2}{0} \cdot n^2 - 1 \cdot \binom{2}{1} \cdot n^1 + 7 \cdot \binom{2}{2} \cdot n^0 \\
n^3 - 3n^2 + 21n - 55 &= 1 \cdot \binom{3}{0} \cdot n^3 + 1 \cdot \binom{3}{1} \cdot n^2 + 7 \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot n^1 + 55 \cdot \binom{3}{3} \cdot n^0 \\
n-2 &= 1 \cdot \binom{1}{0} \cdot n^1 - 2 \cdot \binom{1}{1} \cdot n^0 \\
n^2 - 4n + 10 &= 1 \cdot \binom{2}{0} \cdot n^2 - 2 \cdot \binom{2}{1} \cdot n^1 + 10 \cdot \binom{2}{2} \cdot n^0 \\
n^3 - 6n^2 + 30n - 80 &= 1 \cdot \binom{3}{0} \cdot n^3 + 2 \cdot \binom{3}{1} \cdot n^2 + 10 \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot n^1 + 80 \cdot \binom{3}{3} \cdot n^0
\end{aligned}$$

The general formula is here.

Theorem 5.1. For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} A^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n+1} + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} B^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_n \\ &\quad + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} C^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n-1} - (-1)^m (bA^{(m)} + aB^{(m)} + (c-b)C^{(m)}). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The case where $m = 0$ follows from the identity (10). Now, let $m \geq 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i &= \sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_i \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n (n-i)^m G_{n-i} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j} i^j G_{n-i} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j} \sum_{i=0}^n i^j G_{n-i}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i = \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j} \mathcal{T}_n^{(j)}. \quad (17)$$

Replacing m by j in (14), we get

$$\mathcal{T}_n^{(j)} = A^{(j)} G_{n+1} + B^{(j)} G_n + C^{(j)} G_{n-1} + a n^j - \sum_{r=0}^j (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{j}{r} n^{j-r}.$$

Substituting this in (17) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} A^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n+1} + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} B^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_n \\ &\quad + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} C^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n-1} + a \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} n^m \\ &\quad - \sum_{j=0}^m \sum_{r=0}^j (-1)^j (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} n^{m-r}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} = 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} A^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n+1} + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} B^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_n \\ &\quad + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} C^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n-1} - \psi^{*,(m)}(n), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\psi^{*,(m)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^m \sum_{r=0}^j (-1)^j (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} n^{m-r}. \quad (18)$$

To complete the proof, we need to show that

$$\psi^{*,(m)}(n) = (-1)^m (bA^{(m)} + aB^{(m)} + (c-b)C^{(m)}).$$

By switching the order of summation in (18), we get

$$\begin{aligned}\psi^{*(m)}(n) &= \sum_{r=0}^m \sum_{j=r}^m (-1)^j (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} n^{m-r} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^m (bA^{(r)} + aB^{(r)} + (c-b)C^{(r)}) \left(\sum_{j=r}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} \right) n^{m-r} \\ &= (-1)^m (bA^{(m)} + aB^{(m)} + (c-b)C^{(m)}),\end{aligned}$$

as desired. Here the last equality follows from the binomial identity

$$\sum_{j=r}^m \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} (-1)^j = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } r \neq m; \\ (-1)^m, & \text{if } r = m, \end{cases}$$

from Gould's collection [7, Identity (3.119)]. This completes the proof. $\square$

Corollary 5.2. *For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{i=1}^n i^m N_i &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} A^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) N_{n+1} + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} B^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) N_n \\ &\quad + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} C^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) N_{n-1} - (-1)^m A^{(m)}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. It follows from Theorem 5.1 by setting $G_n \equiv N_n$ and $(a, b, c) = (0, 1, 1)$. $\square$

5.1 Coefficient Polynomials

In fact, the sequences $(A^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$, $(B^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$, and $(C^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$ are inter-related. Consequently, we need only one of these three sequences to find the closed form formula for the Brousseau sums of Narayana numbers. We first define the following three polynomials in order to demonstrate this:

Definition 5.3. *For all integers $m, n \geq 0$, we define the coefficient polynomials, $\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n)$, $\mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(n)$, and $\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n)$, in n of degree m as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n) &= \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j A^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}, \\ \mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(n) &= \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j B^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}, \\ \mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) &= \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j C^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}.\end{aligned}$$

Note that $\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0) = (-1)^m A^{(m)}$, $\mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(0) = (-1)^m B^{(m)}$, and $\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(0) = (-1)^m C^{(m)}$.

Lemma 5.4. *The sequence $(A^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$ is the binomial transform of the sequence $(C^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$. In other words,*

$$A^{(m)} = \sum_{j=0}^m C^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} \quad \text{and} \quad (-1)^m C^{(m)} = \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j A^{(j)} \binom{m}{j}. \quad (19)$$

Proof. The proof is by induction on m . The case where $m = 0$ follows from the fact that $A^{(0)} = C^{(0)} = 1$. Now, let $m \geq 1$. Assume that (19) holds for all non-negative integers less than m . By Definition 4.1,

$$A^{(m)} = \sum_{j=1}^m (1 - (-2)^j) \binom{m}{j} A^{(m-j)}. \quad (20)$$

By induction hypothesis, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we have

$$A^{(m-j)} = \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} C^{(r)} \binom{m-j}{r}.$$

Substituting in (20) yields

$$A^{(m)} = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r=0}^{m-j} (1 - (-2)^j) C^{(r)} \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r}. \quad (21)$$

By executing the change of variable $r' = r + j$ in (21), we get

$$A^{(m)} = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{r'=j}^m (1 - (-2)^j) C^{(r'-j)} \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r'-j}.$$

By switching the order of summation and using the binomial identity [2, Identity 134]

$$\binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{r'-j} = \binom{m}{m-j} \binom{m-j}{r'-j} = \binom{m}{r'} \binom{r'}{j},$$

this becomes

$$\begin{aligned} A^{(m)} &= \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} \sum_{j=1}^{r'} (1 - (-2)^j) C^{(r'-j)} \binom{r'}{j} \\ &= \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} (C^{(r')} - (-1)^{r'}) \quad (\text{By Definition 4.1}) \\ &= \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} C^{(r')} - \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} (-1)^{r'} \\ &= \sum_{r'=1}^m \binom{m}{r'} C^{(r')} + 1 \\ &= \sum_{r'=0}^m \binom{m}{r'} C^{(r')}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the induction step. □

Lemma 5.5. *The sequence $(C^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$ is the binomial transform of the sequence $(B^{(m)})_{m \geq 0}$. In other words,*

$$C^{(m)} = \sum_{j=0}^m B^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} \quad \text{and} \quad (-1)^m B^{(m)} = \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j C^{(j)} \binom{m}{j}.$$

Proof. Similar to Lemma 5.4. □

Proposition 5.6. *For all integers $m, n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) = \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+1).$$

Proof. By Definition 5.3, we have

$$\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j C^{(j)} \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}.$$

Using Lemma 5.5, this becomes

$$\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^m \sum_{r=0}^j (-1)^r \binom{j}{r} A^{(r)} \binom{m}{j} n^{m-j}.$$

By switching the order of summation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) &= \sum_{r=0}^m (-1)^r A^{(r)} \sum_{j=r}^m \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} n^{m-j} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^m (-1)^r A^{(r)} \binom{m}{r} (n+1)^{m-r},\end{aligned}$$

where the last equality follows from the binomial identity,

$$\sum_{j=r}^m \binom{m}{j} \binom{j}{r} n^{m-j} = \binom{m}{r} (n+1)^{m-r},$$

from Gould's collection [7, Identity (3.118)]. Thus

$$\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) = \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+1).$$

This completes the proof. □

Proposition 5.7. *For all integers $m, n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(n) = \mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n+1) = \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+2).$$

Proof. Similar to Proposition 5.6. □

Theorem 5.8. *For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i &= \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n) G_{n+1} + \mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(n) G_n + \mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) G_{n-1} \\ &\quad - (b\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0) + a\mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(0) + (c-b)\mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(0)).\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Follows from Theorem 5.1 and Definition 5.3. □

Corollary 5.9. *For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i^m N_i = \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n) N_{n+1} + \mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(n) N_n + \mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n) N_{n-1} - \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0).$$

Proof. It follows by setting $G_n \equiv N_n$ and $(a, b, c) = (0, 1, 1)$ in Theorem 5.8. □

Theorem 5.10. *For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_i &= \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n) G_{n+1} + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+2) G_n + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+1) G_{n-1} \\ &\quad - (b\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0) + a\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(2) + (c-b)\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(1)).\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Follows from Theorem 5.8, Proposition 5.6, and Proposition 5.7. □

Corollary 5.11. *For all integers $m \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i^m N_i = \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n) N_{n+1} + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+2) N_n + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+1) N_{n-1} - \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0).$$

Proof. It follows by setting $G_n \equiv N_n$ and $(a, b, c) = (0, 1, 1)$ in Theorem 5.10. □

6 Shifted Brousseau Sums

In this section, we find expressions for the shifted Brousseau sums $\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i}$, for all integers $m, r \geq 0$.

Theorem 6.1. *For all integers $m, r \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i} &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} A^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n+r+1} + \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} B^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n+r} \\ &+ \left(\sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} C^{(j)} n^{m-j} \right) G_{n+r-1} - (-1)^m (A^{(m)} G_{r+1} + B^{(m)} G_r + C^{(m)} G_{r-1}). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Proof. The case where $r = 0$ follows from Theorem 5.1. Assume that $r \geq 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i} &= \sum_{i=r+1}^{r+n} (i-r)^m G_i \\ &= \sum_{i=r+1}^{r+n} \sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} i^{m-j} (-r)^j G_i \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=r+1}^{r+n} i^{m-j} G_i \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i} = \sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \left(\sum_{i=1}^{r+n} i^{m-j} G_i - \sum_{i=1}^r i^{m-j} G_i \right) \quad (23)$$

Using Theorem 5.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^{r+n} i^{m-j} G_i - \sum_{i=1}^r i^{m-j} G_i &= \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} A^{(i)} (n+r)^{m-j-i} \right) G_{n+r+1} \\ &+ \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} B^{(i)} (n+r)^{m-j-i} \right) G_{n+r} \\ &+ \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} C^{(i)} (n+r)^{m-j-i} \right) G_{n+r-1} \\ &- \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} A^{(i)} r^{m-j-i} \right) G_{r+1} \\ &- \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} B^{(i)} r^{m-j-i} \right) G_r \\ &- \left(\sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} C^{(i)} r^{m-j-i} \right) G_{r-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting in (23) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i} &= \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} A^{(i)} (n+r)^{m-j-i} \right) G_{n+r+1} \\
&+ \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} B^{(i)} (n+r)^{m-j-i} \right) G_{n+r} \\
&+ \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} C^{(i)} (n+r)^{m-j-i} \right) G_{n+r-1} \\
&- \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} A^{(i)} r^{m-j-i} \right) G_{r+1} \\
&- \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} B^{(i)} r^{m-j-i} \right) G_r \\
&- \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \binom{m}{j} (-r)^j \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-1)^i \binom{m-j}{i} C^{(i)} r^{m-j-i} \right) G_{r-1}.
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

If we write

$$\sum_A(x) = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=0}^{m-j} (-r)^j (-1)^i A^{(i)} \binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{i} x^{m-j-i}, \tag{25}$$

then (24) takes the form

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{i+r} &= \sum_A(n+r) G_{n+r+1} + \sum_B(n+r) G_{n+r} + \sum_C(n+r) G_{n+r-1} \\
&- \sum_A(r) G_{r+1} - \sum_B(r) G_r - \sum_C(r) G_{r-1}.
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Now, using the binomial identity (see [2, Identity 134])

$$\binom{m}{j} \binom{m-j}{i} = \binom{m}{m-j} \binom{m-j}{i} = \binom{m}{i} \binom{m-i}{j},$$

and by switching the order of summation, (25) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_A(x) &= \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^i A^{(i)} \binom{m}{i} \sum_{j=0}^{m-i} \binom{m-i}{j} x^{m-j-i} (-r)^j \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^i A^{(i)} \binom{m}{i} (x-r)^{m-i}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\sum_A(n+r) = \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^i A^{(i)} \binom{m}{i} n^{m-i}, \tag{27}$$

$$\sum_B(n+r) = \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^i B^{(i)} \binom{m}{i} n^{m-i}, \tag{28}$$

$$\sum_C(n+r) = \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^i C^{(i)} \binom{m}{i} n^{m-i}, \tag{29}$$

$$\sum_A(r) = (-1)^m A^{(m)}, \tag{30}$$

$$\sum_B(r) = (-1)^m B^{(m)}, \quad (31)$$

and

$$\sum_C(r) = (-1)^m C^{(m)}. \quad (32)$$

Now, (23) follows by substituting (27) – (32) in (26). $\square$

Corollary 6.2. *For all integers $m, r \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i} &= \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n)G_{n+r+1} + \mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(n)G_{n+r} + \mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(n)G_{n+r-1} \\ &\quad - (\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0)G_{r+1} + \mathcal{P}_B^{(m)}(0)G_r + \mathcal{P}_C^{(m)}(0)G_{r-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Follows from Theorem 6.1 and Definition 5.3. $\square$

Corollary 6.3. *For all integers $m, r \geq 0$, the following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i} &= \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n)G_{n+r+1} + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+2)G_{n+r} + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(n+1)G_{n+r-1} \\ &\quad - (\mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(0)G_{r+1} + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(2)G_r + \mathcal{P}_A^{(m)}(1)G_{r-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Follows from Corollary 6.2, Proposition 5.6, and Proposition 5.7. $\square$

7 Conclusion

In this research, we explored the explicit formulas for the Brousseau sums $\sum_{i=0}^n i^m G_i$ and the shifted Brousseau sums $\sum_{i=1}^n i^m G_{r+i}$ of the generalized Narayana numbers. This involved utilizing straightforward recursion formulas that only require binomial coefficients. The scope of this investigation could be broadened to encompass the general third-order linear recurrence $R_n = pR_{n-1} + qR_{n-2} + rR_{n-3}$ for $n \geq 3$, where $R_0 = a$, $R_1 = b$, and $R_2 = c$.

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References

- [1] K. Adegoke, On Ledin and Brousseau’s summation problems, arxiv preprint arXiv: 2108.04113 [math.CO], 2022. Available at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.04113>
- [2] A. T. Benjamin and J. J. Quinn, *Proofs that really count: The art of combinatorial proof*. 1st ed., vol. 27, Mathematical Association of America, 2003.
- [3] A. Brousseau, Problem H-17, *Fibonacci Quart.* **1** (1963), 55.
- [4] A. Brousseau, Summation of $\sum_{k=1}^n k^m F_{k+r}$ finite difference approach, *Fibonacci Quart.* **5** (1967), 91–98.

- [5] G. Dresden, On the Brousseau sums $\sum_{i=0}^n i^p F_i$, *Integers* **22** (2022).
- [6] J. Erbacher and J. A. Fuchs, Solution to problem H-17, *Fibonacci Quart.* **2** (1964), 51.
- [7] H. W. Gould, *Combinatorial Identities*, Revised edition published by the author, 1972.
- [8] G. Ledin, On a certain kind of Fibonacci sums, *Fibonacci Quart.* **5** (1967), 45–58.
- [9] R. L. Ollerton and A. G. Shannon, A note on Ledin’s summation problem, *Fibonacci Quart.* **58** (2020), 190–199.
- [10] A. G. Shannon and R. L. Ollerton, A note on Ledin’s summation problem, *Fibonacci Quart.* **59** (2021), 47–56.
- [11] Y. Soykan, On generalized Narayana numbers, *Int. J. Adv. Appl. Math. Mech.* **7(3)** (2020), 43–56.
- [12] N. J. A. Sloane et al., The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, 2023. Published electronically at <https://oeis.org>.
- [13] D. Zeitlin, On summation formulas and identities for Fibonacci numbers, *Fibonacci Quart.* **5** (1967), 1–43